

Abstract**Progress Toward HIV Epidemic Control in Bauchi State, Nigeria: An Assessment of ART, TB/HIV, and Key Population Services**

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Background: Nigeria's journey toward HIV epidemic control hinges on more than treatment expansion; it requires sustained viral suppression, strong retention, and integration of preventive and comorbidity services. Understanding how these elements interact at the subnational level is essential to tracking progress and identifying service gaps. This study assessed the 2024 HIV programme performance in Bauchi State. This study aimed to assess progress toward HIV epidemic control in Bauchi State through evaluation of ART retention, viral suppression, and integration of key HIV-related services.

Material and Methods: De-identified facility-level data for 2024 were extracted from the national HIV repository. Indicators included ART enrolment, retention, viral load coverage and suppression, TB and cervical cancer screening, and key population performance.

Results: A total of 28,711 PLHIV were on ART (9,541 males; 19,170 females). Among them,

3,471 (12.1%) had interrupted contact, 948 (3.3%) were lost to follow-up, 284 (1.0%) transferred out, 174 (0.6%) died, and 7 (<0.1%) stopped treatment, yielding 83% retention. Viral load coverage was 84.6% (24,278) with 98.5% (23,918) suppression, 99.9% in males and 97.8% in females. All clients were screened for TB; 686 (1.5%) were presumptive, 72 (0.16%) confirmed active TB, and 384 (0.8%) commenced preventive treatment. Among 19,170 women on ART, 3,168 (16.5%) underwent cervical cancer screening, 15 (0.47%) were positive, and 4 (0.13%) were referred for further evaluation. Key populations comprised 7,059 (24.6%) ART clients; 5,381 (76%) had viral load results, of whom 5,373 (99.9%) achieved suppression.

Conclusion: Bauchi State demonstrated strong viral suppression and retention among ART clients, including key populations. However, suboptimal cervical cancer screening and missed clinical contacts indicate integration gaps. Enhancing preventive screening, patient follow-up, and differentiated service delivery remains vital to consolidate progress toward HIV epidemic control.

Keywords: HIV, ART, Viral Load Suppression, TB/HIV, Cervical Cancer Screening, Key Populations, Nigeria

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